

Multifunctional Structural Green Nanocomposites: An Overview

M. Misra^{1,2}, M. O. Seydibeyoglu², A. K. Mohanty^{1,2}

¹School of Engineering, Thornbrough Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G-2W1, ON Canada

²Bioproducts Discovery and Development Centre, Department of Plant Agriculture, Crop Science Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G-2W1, ON Canada
E mail: mmisra@uoguelph.ca

SUMMARY

This review addresses the recent developments in thermoset nanocomposites with special emphasis on sustainability. The structural applications of these materials require a sustainable approach to creating green products. Green materials are very important to form environment friendly from renewable resources and decrease the use of petroleum based chemicals. New developments in nanotechnology and biotechnology field create sustainable materials such as biobased resins and blends of nanocomposites for structural and other applications.

Keywords: Thermosets, nanocomposites, biobased resins, sustainable materials

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric materials with enhanced properties and functionalities attract much attention for the materials world serving many different industries. Among the various polymer families, thermoset polymers are a very important class especially for structural applications such as aeronautical, automotive, farming, marine, and wind mill applications. One of the most important properties of these materials is the high specific strength (strength/density) which allows them to compete with metallic materials and eventually replace the metallic materials [1, 2].

Moreover, the composite materials prepared with thermoset resins have very high strength values making them ideal structural elements for various applications. The composite materials are created with different processing techniques, and reinforcing phases. One of the advantages of the thermoset materials are the ease of processing, being one of the reasons that these resins are widely used [2, 3].

With the recent developments in the nanotechnology, the nanocomposites offer numerous advantages compared to the conventional composite materials especially using less reinforcement to produce more sustainable structures with improved toughness [4]. The nanocomposites are prepared with various nano size reinforcing phases and with different processes which are similar to the conventional thermoset

processing [5]. Concurrently, new developments in biotechnology and biobased materials offer environment friendly, sustainable, renewable solution applications like aerospace and transportation [6, 7].

In this review, the thermoset composites will be presented with special emphasis on the sustainability of the composite materials with the advancement of the nanotechnology and biotechnology. This review will address the possible applications of nanocomposite materials with their recent developments. To give one specific example of the overarching importance of this area is the application of these materials in wind mills. While producing clean and renewable energy, the materials used for the manufacturing of the wind mill would be also be sustainable and renewable. More details and applications of other developments are presented with the recent developments.

THERMOSET MATERIALS AND COMPOSITES

In the thermosetting polymers, phenolic resins were the first materials synthesized and commercially available in 1907. They are still used today due to their low cost, easy manufacturing techniques, thermal insulation properties, and good flame retardancy, dimensional stability, and chemical resistance. These properties enable this class of products to be used in many different applications such as structural, electronics, and adhesive [8].

Among the thermoset resins, unsaturated polyesters have been widely used due to ease of handling, easy processing, good mechanical, chemical, and electrical properties, and low cost [6, 7, 9]. These properties, and especially comparatively low cost make this polymer useful in a range of applications.

Compared to other thermosetting polymers, epoxy resins have the best performance in the highest mechanical properties, high chemical resistance, and low shrinkage. They find applications in structural, composites, electronics, adhesives, and coatings [10].

Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) are the commonly used composite materials. The fibres are the load carrying materials while the matrix is the load transfer medium surrounding the fibres. FRPs have high specific strength with low density and high strength and modulus. FRPs have been used in different applications like structural and transportation [11, 12]. Composites of the thermosetting materials have been used since the 1950s; especially glass fibre reinforced unsaturated polyester composites [13]. One of the commonly used thermoset composite structure is shown in Figure 1. It is honeycomb structure which is inspired from bees, combining the lightness and high strength in one material.

Figure 1: Conventional thermoset composite material with honeycomb structure

THERMOSET NANOCOMPOSITES

Nanocomposites attract much attention due to the increased mechanical properties with increased toughness values. Nanocomposites are composite materials with the scale of dispersed phase being less than 100 nm, for at least in one dimension. There are various nano size materials used for the preparation of thermosetting nanocomposites. The major nano reinforcements for thermosetting materials are mainly nano clays and carbon nano particles. Silica and alumina have been used for some thermoplastics but research with thermosets is limited with nano alumina [14] and nano silica [15-17].

There are studies reported with nano particles for polymer matrices but dispersion of these nano particles is one of the biggest challenges for the nanocomposites. There have been studies [18-20] to overcome the dispersion problems in the nanocomposites. Kang et al. [18] used sol-gel techniques to incorporate nano silica into the epoxy resin. Liu et al. [19] compared the direct mixing and high pressure mixing to observe the differences in the dispersion of the nanoclays. They observed that high pressure mixing was much more efficient in the dispersion due to the breakage of the clay layers. Sumfleth et al. [20] observed that using titanate modification for carbon nanotubes resulted in better dispersion. It was also noted that besides microscopy techniques, rheology and electrical measurements were helpful in the determination of efficient dispersion.

Exfoliated and intercalated structures are two major types of clay nanocomposites, the [21-24]. In the intercalated structure, the clay layers are partially separated and the polymer can diffuse slightly into the galleries of the clay, whereas in the exfoliated structure, the clay layers are well delaminated and dispersed obtaining a nanocomposite with maximum interaction of the clay and the polymer matrix [25]. The exfoliation of the clays in thermosetting resins depends on the chemistry of the clay and thermosetting material, catalytic effect on the curing reaction, and the miscibility of the clay with the curing agent [4].

There have been studies on thermoset-clay nanocomposites to improve the toughness and tensile strength of the materials [26-31]. Ray et al. [26] has shown that they obtained exfoliated structures with clays in the vinyl ester material up to 5 wt % of clay and they observed intercalation of clays at 10 wt %. Kowalczyk and Szychaj [27] optimized the epoxy clay nanocomposite coating with different epoxies and clays. Gang et al. [28] has studied the dispersion effects for both nanoclays and long fibres with epoxy and they have optimized hybrid composites of micron and nano size fillers. Dean et al. [29] studied the chemorheology of the epoxy-clay nanocomposites and they have discovered that intergallery diffusion and catalyzation of the curing process are essential for the exfoliation of the silicate layers. Kaynak and Tasan [30] optimized processing conditions for clay nanocomposite production method with phenolic resins. Mironi-Harpaz et al. [31] studied critical aspects of curing for unsaturated polyesters.

There have been studies with carbon nanomaterials to prepare nanocomposites with thermosets, as the carbon nanomaterials. Carbon nanotubes attract much attention due to the very high mechanical strength and electrical conductivity [20, 32-35]. As mentioned before, Sumfleth et al [20] used titanate to disperse the carbon nanotubes in epoxy matrix. Chen et al. [32] studied epoxy-multi walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and discovered that carbon nano tubes (CNT) can be used to introduce stiff or flexible interphase depending on the surface grafts and the interaction with the polymer matrix. Seyhan et al. [33] studied the CNT nanocomposites with unsaturated polyester trying to optimize the process, dispersion, and the interphase. Gryshchuk et al. [34] has discovered that the disentangling of CNT in vinyl ester can be achieved with proper processing and MWCNT affects the interphase in the composite material. Tao et al. [35] has worked on the curing processes for the epoxy-CNT nanocomposites with three different CNTs.

BIOBASED THERMOSET NANOCOMPOSITES

Nanocomposites help to manufacture sustainable materials and structures with improved mechanical properties and certain functionalities. Currently, scientists are trying to develop thermoset nanocomposites from biobased resins bringing the sustainable growth one step further, minimizing the dependence on petroleum based resins and helping the environment with vegetable oil based chemicals and polyols [36-37]. Vegetable oil based thermosets have been known for certain time but recent studies show that nanocomposites can be prepared with the vegetable oil based resins [38-44]. Haq et al. [38] studied the processing techniques for biobased unsaturated polyester/clay nanocomposites and determined tensile properties, efficiency, and limits of the process. Haq et al. [39] determined the material properties of the unsaturated polyester/clay nanocomposites with different techniques and determined the optimum concentrations. Miyagawa et al. [40-41] modified epoxy resin linseed oil, reinforced with nanoclays and followed by carbon fibres.

Miyagawa et al. [42] investigated the fracture surfaces of the vegetable oil based clay nanocomposites to understand the structure of the nanocomposites. Miyagawa et al. [43] formulated novel biobased carbon nanocomposites with fluorinated single wall carbon nanotubes and observed that with extremely low content of carbon nanotubes (0.24 wt

%), storage modulus values increased 14 % thus providing evidence of the fine dispersion of the nanotubes with sonication technique. Very low content of nanotubes increase the modulus values significantly with an increase in the epoxidized linseed oil content.

Lu and Wool [44] toughened the triglyceride based thermosets with different fillers; nanoclay being the best compared to liquid rubber and epoxidized soybean liquid. Takada et al. [45] prepared biobased epoxy nanocomposites with natural clays successfully. Biobased resins are now one of the main challenges for the materials science community serving different applications trying to maximize the biologic resource content and decreasing the petroleum based content to minimum levels.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Polymeric materials offer new possibilities and challenges, for all types of materials having the capability to replace different classes such as metallic, ceramic, and wood with the combination of different properties in the form of composites/nanocomposites. The new materials will be composed of nanoenhancements having optimized properties with the rapid developments in the plant based materials for more sustainable and environmentally friendly materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Manju Misra and Amar K. Mohanty are thankful to Ontario Soybean Growers (OSG), Ontario, Canada for the 2008 OSG fund and the Premier's Research Chair Fund, University of Guelph for their financial supports. Amar K. Mohanty and M. Ozgur Seydibeyoglu are thankful for Ministry of Research and Innovation of Ontario, Canada for the post-doctoral research fellowship.

References

1. C. Zilg, R. Mulhaupt, J. Finter, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.*; 200, 661-670 (1999).
2. D. Kong, C. E. Park, *Chem. Mater.*; 15, 419-424 (2003).
3. L. Ruiz-Perez, G. J. Royston, J. P. A. Fairclough, A. J. Ryan, *Polymer*; 49, 4475-4488 (2008).
4. S. Pavlidou, C.D. Papaspyrides, *Prog. Polym. Sci.*; 33, 1119–1198 (2008).
5. O. Becker, R. Varley, G. Simon, *Polymer*; 43, 4365-4375 (2002).
6. H. Miyagawa, A.K. Mohanty, R. Burgueño, L.T. Drzal, M. Misra, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*; 45, 1014-1018 (2006).
7. H. Miyagawa, A.K. Mohanty, R. Burgueño, L.T. Drzal, M. Misra, *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol*; 6, 464-471 (2006).
8. L. González, F. Ferrando, X. Ramis, J. M. Salla, A. Mantecóna, A. Serra, *Prog. Org. Coat.*; 65, 175-181 (2009).

9. A. Gardziella, L.A. Pilato, A. Knop, *Phenolic Resins: Chemistry, Applications, Standardization, Safety, and Ecology*; Springer-Verlag: New York, 1999.
10. M. Bakar, F. Djaider, *J. Thermoplast. Compos. Mater.*; 20, 53-64 (2007).
11. A. Buekers, E. V. Hinte, 010 Publishers, 2005, p.15.
12. J.F. Monk, *Thermosetting Plastics*, 2nd ed.; Addison WesleyLongman: Great Britain, 1997.
13. H. Lee, K. Neville, *Handbook of Epoxy Resins*; McGraw-Hill: New York/San Francisco, 1967.
14. P.K. Mallick, *Fiber-Reinforced Composites*; Marcel Dekker: New York, 1988.
15. S. Zhao, L. S. Schadler, R. Duncan, H. Hillborg, T. Auletta, *Comp. Sci. Tech.*; 68, 2965-2975 (2008).
16. T. Mahrholz, J. Stängle, M. Sinapius, *Comp. Part A*; 40, 235–243 (2009).
17. P. Rosso, L. Ye, K. Friedrich, S. Sprenger, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*; 100, 1849-1855 (2006).
18. S. Kang, S.I. Hong, C.R. Choe, M. Park, S. Rim, J. Kim, *Polymer*; 42, 879-887 (2001).
19. W. Liu, S. V. Hoa, M. Pugh, *Comp. Sci. Tech.*; 65, 307-316 (2005).
20. J. Sumfleth, L.A.S.A. Prado, M. Sriyai, K. Schulte, *Polymer*; 49, 5105-5112 (2008).
21. H. Zhang, L.C. Tang, Z. Zhang, K. Friedrich, S. Sprenger, *Polymer*; 49, 3816-3825 (2008).
22. X. Wang, Z. Qi, F. Wang, *Eng. Plast. Appl.*; 27, 1 (1998).
23. Z. Wang, T. Lan, T. Pinnavaia, *Chem. Mater.*; 8, 2200-2204 (1996).
24. P. B. Messersmith, E.P. Giannelis, *Chem. Mater.*; 6, 1719-1725 (1994).
25. R. Krishnamoorti, R.A. Vaia, E.P. Giannelis, *Chem. Mater.*; 8, 1728-1734 (1996).
26. D. Ray, S. Sengupta, S. P. Sengupta, A. K. Mohanty, M. Misra, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.*; 291, 1513-1520 (2006).
27. K. Kowalczyk, T. Szychaj, *Prog. Org. Coat.*; 62, 425-429 (2008).
28. G. Zhou, S. Movva, L. J. Lee, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*; 108, 3720-3726 (2008).
29. D. Dean, R. Walker, M. Theodore, E. Hampton, E. Nyairo, *Polymer*, 46, 3014-3021 (2005).
30. C. Kaynak, C. C. Tasan, *Eur. Polym. J.*; 42, 1908-1921 (2006).
31. I. Mironi-Harpaz, M. Narkis, A. Siegmann, *Macromol. Symp.*; 242, 201-207 (2006).
32. W. Chen, H. Lu, S. R. Nutt, *Comp. Sci. Tech.*; 68, 2535-2542 (2008).
33. A. T. Seyhan, F. H. Gojny, M. Tanoglu, K. Schulte, *E.Polym. J.*; 43, 374-379 (2007).

34. O. Gryshchuk, J. Karger-Kocsis, R. Thomann, Z. Konya, I. Kiricsi, *Comp. Part A*; 37, 1252-1259 (2006).
35. K. Tao, S. Yang, J. C. Grunlan, Y.S. Kim, B. Dang, Y. Deng, R. L. Thomas, B. L. Wilson, X. Wei, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*; 102, 5248-5254 (2006).
36. R. Burgueno, M. J. Quagliata, A. K. Mohanty, G. Mehta, L. T. Drzal, M. Misra, *Mat. Sci. Eng. A*; 390, 178-187 (2005).
37. R. Burgueno, M. J. Quagliata, A.K. Mohanty, G. Mehta, L. T. Drzal, M. Misra *Comp. Part A*; 36, 581-593 (2005).
38. M. Haq, R. Burgueno, A. K. Mohanty, M. Misra, *Comp. Part A*; 40, 394-403 (2009).
39. M. Haq, R. Burgueno, A. K. Mohanty, M. Misra, *Comp. Part A*; 40, 540-547 (2009).
40. H. Miyagawa, M. Misra, L. T. Drzal, A.K. Mohanty, *Polymer*; 46, 445-453 (2005).
41. H. Miyagawa, R. J. Jurek, A. K. Mohanty, M. Misra, L. T. Drzal, *Comp. Part A*; 37, 54-62 (2006).
42. H. Miyagawa, M. Misra, L. T. Drzal, A. K. Mohanty, *J. Polym. Env.*; 13, 87-96 (2005).
43. H. Miyagawa, A.K. Mohanty, L. T Drzal, M. Misra, *Nanotechnology*; 16, 118-124 (2005).
44. J. Lu, R. P. Wool, *Comp. Sci. Tech.*; 68, 1025-1033 (2008).
45. Y. Takada, K. Shinbo, Y. Someya, M. Shibata, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*; 113, 479-484 (2009).